

Cyanide Biodegradation Potentials of Microbial Isolates from Cassava Processing Wastewater

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Abstract

Nigeria, the world's largest producer of cassava, *Manihot esculenta* (Crantz) very unfortunately, has consistently generated so much waste from cassava mills which are usually discharged on land or water indiscriminately and this in turn, affects the biota, especially in the southern part of the country where most of the mills are located. The cassava tuber contain significant amounts of hydrocyanic acid which is highly toxic to humans and animals. Biological methods harness the metabolic capabilities of some microorganisms that naturally use pollutants, as a source of nitrogen. The availability and accessibility of pollutants as substrates for microbial degradation are critical for bioremediation success. This study was aimed at isolating and characterizing of microorganisms that is able to use cyanide as nitrogen source from cassava wastewater, using mineral salt agar. Cassava wastewater and soil samples were collected from local Cassava Mill garri processing Plant located at Amansea, Awka-North and Amaenyi, Awka-South Local Government of Anambra State. Microbial isolation and identification were done using standard methods. Data were analyzed using one way ANOVA and Turkey test at $P < 0.05$. Among the microbial strains isolated from the liquid effluent of cassava processing factories, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Paenibacillus sordelli* were able to degrade 87.50%, 83.33%, 84.38%, 79.16% in media containing 1ml of cassava waste water and 84.41%, 83.87%, 81.72%, 74.19% in media containing 0.5ml of cassava waste water. The study clearly demonstrates the potential of aerobic treatment with cyanide degrading microorganism for cyanide removal in cassava factory wastewaters. This will create a safe and friendly environment in communities where cassava tubers are processed into products.

Keywords Biodegradation, Potential, Mineral Salt Agar, Cyanide, Microorganism

1. Introduction

Root and tuber crops, including cassava, sweet potato, potato, and yam, constitute major food crops for direct human consumption across Africa. Cultivated across diverse agroecologies and production systems (Agu *et al.*, 2014; Okigbo *et al.*, 2015; Agu *et al.*, 2023). Cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) is a staple food crop in Nigeria, providing approximately 70% of the daily caloric intake for over 50 million people. Globally, cassava is estimated to be a significant food source for over 500 million individuals (Agu *et al.*, 2016; Okonkwo *et al.*, 2023). Cyanides are widely present in biotic and abiotic components of the ecosystem. Cyanide compounds are being used in gold extraction, electroplating industries, synthesis of agrochemicals, etc. Cassava mill effluent also has high cyanide content (Okonkwo *et al.*, 2023). Rapid industrialization has resulted in enormous increase in the amount of cyanides in the environment. According to International Cyanide Management Institute, 1.1 million metric tons of cyanide is produced annually worldwide. Although cyanides have a range of applications, yet they are highly toxic and need to be degraded into nontoxic or less toxic forms. The toxic contaminants leading to ecological imbalance are of global concern (Kour *et al.*, 2021). However, chemical and physical treatments detoxify cyanide at a rapid rate, their applications are limited due to environmental variations, high cost and operational hazards. Biodegradation is the process where microorganisms break down organic matter (Agu *et al.*, 2015, Anaukwu *et al.*, 2016; Okafor *et al.*, 2016). Thus biological method of cyanide removal or precisely bioremediation of cyanide is more attractive. A number of microorganisms (fungi, bacteria and algae) have been reported which use cyanide as sole source of nitrogen or carbon and degrade cyanide to amide or acid. Microbes belonging to genera *Alcaligenes*, *Aspergillus*, *Bacillus*, *Flavobacterium*, *Nocardia*, *Pseudomonas*, *Rhizopus*, *Rhodococcus*, and *Stereum* have been reported to have a potential role in bioremediation (Verma *et al.*, 2019). Bioremediation is the use of microorganisms to destroy or immobilize waste materials. The application of the microbes for bioremediation is a versatile technology with high stability, economical, eco- friendly, lack of interference with the ecology of the ecosystem, and more public acceptance (Singh *et al.*, 2020). Environmental cleaning through bioremediation is a substitute to the physicochemical approaches, which are rather environmentally disparaging and can be the cause of the secondary pollution. Bioremediation could be utilized in cleanup of contaminated sites such as water, soils, sludge, and waste streams (Kour *et al.*, 2021).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the Study Area:

Cassava wastewater and soil samples were collected from local Cassava Mill garri processing Plant located at Amansea, Awka-North and Amaenyi, Awka-South Local Government of Anambra State.

2.2 Sample collection

Cassava waste water samples were collected using random sampling method from four different locations at the Cassava Mill garri processing Plant located at Amansea, Awka-North and Amaenyi, Awka-South Local Government of Anambra State. The Cassava wastewater soil

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samples were collected in sterile bottles and transported immediately in cold storage container to the Laboratory.

2.3 Isolation of Microorganisms

Microbial isolation procedures were conducted on Nutrient and MacConkey Agar plates for bacteria and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar plates for fungi, both agar were supplemented with 1% (v/v) of cassava waste water as carbon source. They were autoclaved at 121⁰C for 15mins before inoculation. Ten –fold serial dilution of homogenized cassava waste water sample were prepared and 0.1 aliquots of the contaminated soil and waste water samples collected, were inoculated into the Nutrient and MacConkey Agar plates. The inoculated plates were incubated at 37⁰C for 48hrs for bacteria and at 30⁰C for 3-5 days for fungi. Pure culture was prepared by inoculating on nutrient agar, using a streak - plate technique. (Mbachu *et al.*, 2018).

2.4 Inoculum Development

Mineral salt broth containing 0.3ml of cassava wastewater was dispensed in 30ml quantities into four 250ml Erlenmeyer flasks. A loopful of the isolates were inoculated into the medium and incubated at 120rpm in a shaker at 30⁰C for 24hrs.

2.5 Biodegradation Assay of Cyanide

Ten (10) milliliter of the inoculums developed was added into each set of four 250ml Erlenmeyer Flasks containing 1ml of cassava wastewater and another set of 250ml Flasks containing 0.5ml of cassava waste water in 100ml of mineral salt medium with the fifth flasks that was two, serving as a control for each of the 1ml and 0.5ml flasks. The two fifth flasks contain only the medium with 1ml and 0.5ml each of st cerilized cassava waste water without any addition of culture from the inoculum development. The cultures in triplicates were incubated at 30⁰C for 15days at 180rpm, in a gyratory shaker. At 5 day interval during the incubation, samples were drawn from the flasks for measurement of optical density at 550nm wavelength, pH and total viable count. (Okpokwasili *et al.*, 1990).

2.6 Degradation Efficiency

The degradation efficiency (DE) of cyanide degrading microbial isolate was calculated as shown in the following formula.

$$DE(\%) = \frac{Ic - Rc}{Ic} \times 100$$

Where Ic = Initial concentration of cyanide (mg/dl) and Rc = Residual concentration of cyanide (mg/dl). (Sujatha *et al.*, 2015).

2.7 Statistical Analysis

Data were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) of three replicates. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test significance of variations within and among the groups. When significant difference was indicated by ANOVA, Tukey test was used for statistical analysis to make pair-wise comparisons between means. A statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software was used for statistical analysis in this study and test for significance between means was implied at $P = 0.05$ level.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Identification of the isolates

Four isolates were obtained in this study. They were identified as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Paeniclostridium sordelli*, based on their morphological, biochemical characteristics and molecular analysis. The acidic nature of the cassava waste water probably favors the growth of the microbial isolates, as these encountered microbial isolates have been reported to be an acid tolerant (Agarry, 2005 and Oboh, 2005).

3.2 Cyanide Degrading Potential of the Isolates

The Microbial isolates were used for cyanide degradation in mineral salt medium. The growth of the microorganism in mineral medium using 1ml cassava waste water as the sole nitrogen source were shown in Figure 1, 2 and 3; while Figure 4, 5 and 6 showed the growth of the microbial isolates in mineral salt medium using 0.5ml cassava waste water as the sole nitrogen source. The growth of the microbial isolates showed an increase in the optical density and total viable count of the isolates, there was also a reduction in the pH of all the isolates during the incubation period.

All of these isolates were able to grow on cassava wastewater as the sole source of nitrogen when screened for cyanide utilization, and were able to degrade the cyanide. This correlated with the report of Izah *et al.*, (2016) and Sujatha *et al.*, (2015) in a similar research.

The growth dynamics of the organisms was determined by the optical densities, total viable counts and the pH of the culture media. The growth and cyanide degradation efficiency of the individual microbial isolates were determined in a mineral salt media supplemented with cassava waste water (0.5ml and 1ml), whereby 1ml of cassava waste water was used in the first set of biodegradation, and 0.5ml in the second set . This was carried out because most organisms may not adapt in high cyanide concentration. After the incubation period, the decrease of cyanide concentration in the medium was concomitant with an increase in cell density (microbial population). The fact that the final cell density obtained was considerably high indicated the use of well acclimatized cyanide metabolizing culture. Also the reduction in pH of the culture fluids in the experimental flasks within the 15day incubation period further confirmed chemical changes of the cassava wastewater substrates which must have been metabolized by microbial enzymes. Even though, an increase in cell density was observed at

higher cassava wastewater concentration, at initial phase the cells needed some period of acclimatization. Particularly, it was observed that the period corresponding to initial microbial adaption phase before starting the cyanide degradation, significantly increased as the initial cassava wastewater concentration is increased.

Higher microbial growth in terms of OD₅₅₀ was obtained with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, *Bacillus thuringiensis* followed by *Paeniclostridium sordelli* in mineral salt media containing cassava wastewater at 1ml concentrations. While in media containing cassava wastewater at 0.5ml concentrations higher microbial growth in terms of OD₅₅₀ was obtained with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, followed by *Paeniclostridium sordelli*.

3.2 Growth of isolates in mineral salt medium containing 1ml of cassava waste water as a sole nitrogen source

Optical Density (550nm)

Fig 1: Variation in optical density with time during degradation of cyanide in mineral salt medium containing 1ml of cassava waste water by the isolates

Total viable count (Cfu/ml)

Fig 2: Variation in total viable count with time during degradation of cyanide in mineral salt medium containing 1ml of cassava waste water by the isolates

Fig 3: Variation in pH with time during degradation of cyanide in mineral salt medium containing 1ml of cassava waste water by the isolate

3.3 Growth of isolates in mineral salt medium containing 0.5ml of cassava waste water

Optical Density

Days of incubation

Fig 4: Variation in optical density with time during degradation of cyanide in mineral salt medium containing 0.5ml of cassava waste water by the isolates

Total viable count (Cfu/ml)

Fig 5: Variation in total viable count with time during degradation of cyanide in mineral salt medium containing 0.5ml of cassava waste water by the isolates

Fig 6: Variation in pH with time during degradation of cyanide in mineral salt medium containing 0.5ml of cassava waste water by the isolates

3.3 Estimation of Cyanide Removal by the Isolates

Table 1 and 2 shows the extent of cyanide removal by the isolates in 1ml concentration of cassava wastewater effluent while table 3 and 4 shows the removal by the isolates in 0.5ml concentration of cassava wastewater effluent. Percentage difference of *Bacillus thuringiensis* which is 83.33% in 1ml and 83.87% in 0.5ml of cassava wastewater was not much, this showed that *Bacillus thuringiensis* can still survive in the two concentration of cassava wastewater but *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* which is 84.38% in 1ml and 81.72% in 0.5ml of cassava wastewater showed that *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* survived more in 1ml of cassava wastewater than that of 0.5ml. Since the overall percentage of all the organisms both in 1ml and 0.5ml concentration of cassava waste water is above 50%, these showed that all the organisms are capable of degrading cyanide in the cassava waste water.

The results clearly showed that microorganisms are associated with the cassava wastewater. This correlated with the report of (Sujatha *et al.*, 2015); in a similar research. The growth and survival of these microbial isolates may not be unconnected with the fact that the waste water contained substances that can be utilized by the isolates (Uzochukwu *et al.* 2001 and Oboh, 2005) had earlier reported in the composition of cassava wastewater.

Table 1: Estimation of Cyanide degradation by isolates in mineral salt medium containing 1ml of cassava wastewater

Isolate	Concentration of Cyanide in control (CC) mg/dl	Concentration of Cyanide degradation after (CAD) mg/dl	Concentration of Cyanide degraded (CD) mg/dl
NG	1.0368	0.1296	0.9072
C2	1.0368	0.1728	0.8640
A2	1.0368	0.162	0.8748
B2	1.0368	0.216	0.820

$$CD = CC - CAD$$

CD = Concentration of Cyanide degraded,

CC = Concentration of Cyanide in control

CAD = Concentration of Cyanide after degradation

Table 2: Total Cyanide degraded expressed in percentage in mineral salt medium containing 1ml of cassava wastewater

Isolate	% Cyanide degraded (%CD)
NG	87.50
C2	83.33
A2	84.38
B2	79.16

$\%CD = CD/CC \times 100$

CD = Concentration of Cyanide degraded,

CC = Concentration of Cyanide in control

KEY

NG = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

C2 = *Bacillus thuringiensis*

A2 = *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*

B2 = *Paeniclostridium sordelli*

Table 3: Estimation of Cyanide degradation by isolates in mineral salt medium containing 0.5ml of cassava wastewater

Isolate	Concentration of Cyanide in control mg/dl	Concentration of Cyanide after degradation mg/dl	Concentration of Cyanide degraded mg/dl
NG	1.0044	0.1566	0.8478
C2	1.0044	0.1620	0.8424
A2	1.0044	0.1836	0.8208
B2	1.0044	0.2592	0.7452

KEY

NG = *Pseudomoas aeruginosa*

C2 = *Bacillus thuringiensis*

A2 = *Stenotrophomonas malophilia*

B2 = *Paeniclostridium sordelli*

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Table 4: Total Cyanide degraded expressed in percentage in mineral medium containing 0.5ml of cassava waste water

Isolate	% Cyanide degraded
NG	84.41
C2	83.87
A2	81.72
B2	74.19

KEY

NG = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

C2 = *Bacillus thuringiensis*

A2 = *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*

B2 = *Paeniclostridium sordelli*

4.0 CONCLUSION

Among the isolates, *Pseudomonas sp.* has greater potential for bioremediation of cyanide from cassava wastewater environment and could serve as a biomaterial for cyanide removal from aqueous solutions. These results showed that aerobic systems can be successfully applied for cyanide removal from aqueous solutions up to high cyanide concentrations. In conclusion, our findings in the course of this research, proves that microbial bioremediation stands as a promising and sustainable approach for addressing environmental pollution and restoring contaminated sites. This method is more efficient and economically friendly than other methods.

References

Agarry, O.O. (2005). Assessment of microorganisms isolated from cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) products as biocontrol agents. Ph.D. Thesis. Federal University of Technology, Akure.

Agu K.C., Awah, N.S., Okeke, C.B., Nwodo, M.T., Anaukwu, C.G., Iloanusi C.A., Archibong, E.J., Ngenegbo, U., Mgbemena, I.C., Umeoduagu, N. (2016). Mycological Deterioration and Pathogenicity Studies of Post-harvest Cassava. Food Science and Technology, 4(2): 23-30, 2016 DOI: 10.13189/fst.2016.040202

Agu, K.C., Awah, N. S., Sampson, P. G., Ikele, M. O., Mbachu, A. E., Ojiagu, K. D., Okeke, C. B., Okoro, N. C. N. and Okafor, O. I. (2014). Identification and Pathogenicity of Rot-

Causing Fungal Pathogens Associated with *Xanthosoma sagittifolium* Spoilage in South Eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture Innovations and Research*, **2** (6): 1155-1159

Agu, K.C., Bassey, E.E., Iloanusi, C.A., Awah, N.S., Okeke, B.C., Anaukwu, C.G., Ezenwa, C.U., Orji, M.U. and Okafor, A.C. (2015). Isolation and Characterization of Microorganisms from Oil Polluted Soil in Kwata, Awka South, Nigeria. *American Journal of Current Microbiology*, **3**: 46-59.

Agu, K.C., Ikwuka, O.I., Umeoduagu, N.D., Victor-Aduloju A.T., Uwanta L.I., Ikenwa, B.O., Nwiyi, I.U., Chidubem-Nwachinemere, N.O., Nwosu, J.C. and Okafor, I.J. (2023). Fermentation and Production of Cocoyam (*Colocasia esculenta*) Flour Fortified with Soybean Powder. *Cognizance Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, **3** (6): 449-470. **DOI: 10.47760/cognizance.2023.v03i06.031**

Agwaranze, D. I., Nwugo, V. O., Ogoto, A. C., Onudibia, M. E., Nwaneri, C. B. and Aliba, N. V. (2018). Effects of cassava mill effluent (CME) on bacteria diversity of soil and aquatic environments in South-South Nigeria. *Open Access Journal of Science*, **2**(4): 238-239

Aiyegoro, O.A., Akinpelu, D.A., Igbinsosa, E.O. and Ogunmwonyi, H.I. (2017). Effect of cassava effluent on the microbial population dynamic and physicochemical characteristic on soil community. *Science Focus*. **12**(1): 98-101.

Anani O.A. and Adetunji C.O. (2021). Bioremediation of polythene and plastics using beneficial microorganisms. *Microbial Rejuvenation of Polluted Environment*.281–302.

Anaukwu, C.G., Ezemba, C.C., Anakwenze, V.N., **Agu, K.C.**, Amechi, S.N., Okeke, B.C., Awah, N.S. (2016). Influence of Anionic, Cationic and Non-Ionic Surfactants on Growth of Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria. *American Journal of Current Microbiology*, **4**:10-16.

Anaukwu, C.G., Ezemba, C.C., Anakwenze, V.N., **Agu, K.C.**, Okeke, B.C., Awah N.S., Ekwealor, I.A. (2016). Effect of biosurfactant produced by *Citrobacter murlinae* AF025369 and a synthetic surfactant on degradation of crude oil. *Edorium Journal of Microbiology*, **2**: 1–6

Attar, A.J. (2015). On the Feasibility of Poisoning with Cyanides and How to Prevent it. Appealing Products Inc.,840 Main Campus Drive, Suit 3530.Raleigh, NC 27606 USA. *E mail: ajattar@appealingproducts.com*

Chamas A. and Tabassum T. (2021). Degradation rates of plastics in the environment. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*. **2020**; **8**:3494– 3511.

Douglas, G. M., Maffei, V. J., Zaneveld, J. R., Yurgel, S. N., Brown, J. R., Taylor, C. M., and Langille, M. G. (2020). PICRUSt2 for prediction of metagenome functions. *Nature biotechnology*, **38(6)**:685-688.

Izah, S. C. Angaye, T.C.N. and Ohimain, E.I. (2016). Environmental impacts of Oil palm processing in Nigeria. *Biotechnological Research*, **2(3)**: 132-141

Jansson, J. K. and Hofmockel, K. S. (2020). Soil microbiomes and climate change. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, **18(1)**:35–46.

Kour, D., Kaur, T., Devi, R., Yadav, A., Singh, M. and Joshi, D. (2021). Beneficial Microbiomes for Bioremediation of Diverse Contaminated Environments for Environmental Sustainability: Present Status and Future Challenges. *Environmental Science Pollution Research*, **28**: 24917-39.

Mbachu, A.E., Chukwura, E.I. and Mbachu, N.A. Evaluation of the effectiveness of fungi (*Candida tropicalis* and *Aspergillus clavatus*) in bioremediation of used engine oil contaminated soil using bioaugmentation technique. *International Journal of Environment, Agriculture and Biotechnology*, 3(4): 11751182, 2018.<http://d>

Nwaugo, V.O., Chinyere, G.C. and Inyang, C.U. (2018). Effects of palm oil mill effluent (POME) on Soil Bacterial Flora and enzyme activities in Egbema. *Plant Products Research Journal*. **12**: 10-13.

Oboh, G. (2005). Isolation and characterization of amylase from fermented cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) wastewater. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, **4**: 1117-1123.

Obueh, H.O. and Odesiri-Eruteyan, E. (2016). A study on the effects of cassava processing wastes on the soil environment of a local cassava mill. *Journal of Pollution Effect and Contamination*. **4**: 177.

Ogunyemi, A.K., Samuel, T.A., Amund, O.O. and Ilori, M.O. (2017) Toxicity evaluation of waste effluent from cassava-processing factory in Lagos state, Nigeria using the *Allium Cepa* Assay. *Ife Journal Science*. **19(2)**:369-377. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ijss.v19i2.17>

Okafor, U.C., Orji, M.U., **Agu, K.C.**, Awah, N.S., Okeke, B.C., Okafor, O.I. and Okoro N.C.N. (2016). Bioremediation of Crude Oil-polluted Soil Using Broiler-Chicken Droppings. *Journal of Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, **4**, (4): 75-84, DOI:10.12691/jaem-4-4-2

Okafor, U.C., Orji, M.U., Nwankwegu, A.S. Anaukwu, C.G., Onuorah, S.C., Archibong, E.J., Obika, I.E. and **Agu, K.C.** (2016). Effect of Chicken droppings amendment on bioremediation of crude oil polluted soil. *European Journal of Experimental Biology*, **6** (4): 62-68.

Okigbo, R.N. Enweremadu, C.E. **Agu, K.C.**, Irondi, R.C., Okeke, B.C., Awah, N.S., Anaukwu, C.G., Okafor, I.O., Ezenwa, C.U., Iloanusi, A.C. (2015). Control of white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) rot pathogen using peel extract of water yam (*Dioscorea alata*). *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 6 (10); 7-13.

Okonkwo, N.N., Okoli, F.A., Agu, K.C., Okeke, C.M., Awari, V.G., Ifediegwu, M.C. and Umeoduagu, N.D. (2023). Identification of Indigenous Bacteria from Soil Contaminated with Cassava Mill Effluents. *International Journal of Progressive Research in Engineering Management and Science*, 3 (9): 393-399

Okpowasili, G. C. and Odokuma, L.O. Effect of salinity on biodegradation of oil spills dispersants. *Waste Management*, 10(2): 141-146, 1990.[https://doi.org/10.1016/0956-053X\(90\)90118-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0956-053X(90)90118-5).

Olukanni, D.O., Adeleke, J.O. and Aremu, D.D. (2016). A Review of Local Factors affecting Solid Waste Collection in Nigeria. *Pollution*, 2: 339–356.

Orji, J.O. and Ayogu, T.E. (2018) Effects of cassava mill effluent on, physico-chemical characteristics and bacterial flora of soil in Ezamgbo Community Ebonyi State Nigeria. *World Journal of Medical Science*. 15 (1): 20-33. <https://doi:10.5829/idosi.wjms.2018.20-33>

Singh, S. and Tiwari, G. (2020). Application of Bioremediation on Solid Waste Management: *A reviewed Journal of Bioremediation*, 5: 19424.

Sujatha K., Balachandar D., Kumar K. and Gero B. (2015). Aerobic cyanide degradation by bacterial isolates from cassava factory wastewater. *Brazilian Journal of Microbiology*. 46(3): 659 -666

Trivedi, P., Schenks, P.M., Wallenstein, M.D. and Singh, B.K. (2019) Tiny microbes, big yields: enhancing food crops production with biological solutions. *Microbial Biotechnology*, 10, (In press). doi: 10.1111/1751-7915.12804.

Uguru, H. and Obah, G.E. (2019). Remediation of effluents from cassava processing mills. *Direct Research Journal of Public Health Environment*. 4(4): 21-25.

Uzochukwu, S.V.A., Oyede, R. and Atanda, O. (2001). Utilization of gari industry effluent in the preparation of a gin. *Nigerian Journal of Microbiology*, 15: 87-92.

Verma, S. and Kuila, A. (2019). Bioremediation of Contaminants by Microbial Process. *Environmental Technological Innovation*, 14:100369.

Wei R. and Zimmermann W. (2017). Microbial enzymes for the recycling of recalcitrant petroleum- based plastics: how far are we? *Microbial Biotechnology*. 10:1308–1322.

Yadav, A.N., Rastegari, A.A., Yadav, N., Kour, D. (2020). Advances in Plant Microbiome and Sustainable Agriculture: Diversity and Biotechnological Applications. *Singapore: Springer*.

Zhang, H., Tang, W., Chen, Y., and Yin, W. (2021). Disinfection threatens aquatic ecosystems science, 368, 146-147.